
X-AMPIE: Expressed Amplification Signatures for Information Exchange in Cancer

Qi Xu¹, Jeanne Kowalski^{1,*}

¹Department of Oncology, Dell Medical School, University of Texas at Austin, Austin, TX, USA

*To whom correspondence should be addressed.

Abstract

Motivation: Gene amplification in cancer often leads to overexpression of certain genes, resulting in uncontrolled cell growth, tumor formation, and cancer progression. In this regard, the amplification of multiple oncogenes lends support to an unfavorable outcome, while multiple tumor suppressor genes, lend support to a more favorable one. In general, the amplification of several genes is likely to contain a mix of canonical and non-canonical genes expressed at varying levels and for which little is known about their recurring co-occurring (RECO) frequency and potential as multi-gene markers with clinical and therapeutic implications.

Result: By building expressed amplification signatures (EASs) within cancer types and model systems (e.g., cell lines, patient, user-define), X-AMPIE is a novel platform to enable a focused, EAS-centric study of their signature enriched exchange of information between them, defined as a crosstalk, and their corresponding RECO EAS signatures. The tool offers a range of functions and visualization techniques for exploring the EAS-derived crosstalk among different cancers and model systems. X-AMPIE's primary modules include: EAS generation, exploration, and cross-talk, with feature selection for informed study. Altogether, X-AMPIE provides a platform in which to solve the problem of deriving and comparing expressed gene amplifications among sample pairs from different model systems and cancer types for effective study design and analyses of their use as potential treatment targets and markers of treatment response and outcome in cancer.

Availability and implementation: The X-AMPIE app is available at <https://kowalski-labapps.dellmed.utexas.edu/GenA/>.

Contact: Jeanne.Kowalski@austin.utexas.edu

Introduction

Cancer remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with its complex and heterogeneous nature posing significant challenges for diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. Among the various molecular mechanisms involved in cancer development and progression, gene amplification plays a critical role (1). Gene amplification refers to the process by which certain genes in cancer cells undergo duplication or amplification, leading to increased expression levels. This overexpression often results in uncontrolled cell growth, tumor formation, and ultimately, cancer progression(1, 2). The identification and analysis of expressed amplification signatures (EASs) in cancer can provide valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms driving cancer and facilitate the development of targeted therapeutic interventions.

The advancements in high-throughput genomic sequencing have led to the generation of large volumes of publicly available cancer data, including gene expression data and copy number alteration data. In this study, we present X-AMPIE, a versatile amplification-focused signature analysis platform designed to generate, explore, and connect EASs in cancer using publicly available resources. X-AMPIE combines information from gene expression and copy number alteration data to identify genes that exhibit both feature characteristics in cancer. By leveraging this information at the sample-level, X-AMPIE offers the ability to explore recurring co-occurring (RECO) EASs for their prevalence and novel gene combinations as signatures in cancer.

The main motivation behind X-AMPIE is to address the challenges associated with understanding the complex landscape of expressed amplification genes in cancer. These genes may co-occur within amplification signatures, but their frequencies and potential as multi-gene markers with clinical and therapeutic implications remain poorly understood. X-AMPIE aims to fill this knowledge gap by identifying sample-specific EASs and extracting recurring, co-occurring genes from them. By doing so, X-AMPIE enables a focused study of co-occurring expressed gene amplifications and their potential as multi-markers with therapeutic implications.

Moreover, X-AMPIE introduces the novel concept of sample-level signature crosstalk within the context of sample-level EASs that allows for the exploration of relations among signatures derived from different cancer types and model systems (e.g., cancer cell lines, patient tumors, user-defined). The novelty here is the use of sample-level signatures from one system or cancer type to build a relation with another set of sample-level signatures from another system or cancer types. Thus, the flexibility in allowing different sample-level signatures and their derived source makes this concept widely applicable to solve many problems outside of the current focus. This novel crosstalk functionality facilitates the exchange of information and insights between different signature sets, including but not limited to EASs, revealing commonalities and interactions with potential therapeutic and clinical outcome implications. By enabling a deeper understanding

of the relationships between gene amplification signatures, X-AMPIE offers researchers the opportunity to uncover novel connections and biological mechanisms underlying cancer progression.

To provide a comprehensive platform for the investigation of EASs, X-AMPIE provides signature generation, exploration, and connection modules. Researchers can generate EAS signatures, explore the prevalence and characteristics of amplified genes within different cancer types and model systems, and analyze the crosstalk between derived sample-level EASs. The tool incorporates user-friendly visualization techniques and interactive functionalities to facilitate intuitive exploration and interpretation of the results.

Altogether, X-AMPIE represents a significant advancement in the field of gene amplification analysis in cancer. Our application demonstrates the novel utility of X-AMPIE in providing a comprehensive platform for the investigation of EASs. By simplifying the process of extracting and analyzing EASs, and offer a way to generally relate them at the sample-level, X-AMPIE allows users to build an amplification architecture of EASs for further research pursuit. Furthermore, the intuitive visualization and versatile functionality of X-AMPIE enable users with varying levels of expertise to effectively utilize the tool, making it a valuable resource for researchers in the cancer research community.

Materials and methods

X-AMPIE is an application that offers a web interface for the analysis and visualization of amplified gene signatures in cancer. Developed using the R/Shiny environment, X-AMPIE provides researchers with a fast and convenient platform for hypothesis generation focused on gene amplifications.

Expression-Amplification Signatures Generation. X-AMPIE is populated with both TCGA (patient data) and CCLE (patient-derived cell line data) to identify genes with high expression and amplification in individual samples (3) and cell lines (1). By default, high expression is determined by normalized gene expression (z-score normalized counts ≥ 2), while amplification is assessed by gene-level copy number (CNA threshold ≥ 1). Users can choose different signature generation options, including gene amplification, mRNA-expressed amplification (RNA-Seq-derived), protein-expressed amplification (RPPA-derived), or a combination of both mRNA and protein expression. Omics data are downloaded from cBioPortal (4) and UCSC Xena (5). Additionally, users have the option to further subset signatures according to inclusion of select gene(s), such as an oncogene, as part of the signature, thus constructing a gene-containing EAS.

Pan-cancer Signature and Survival Analysis. The data used to create the expressed amplification signatures for this pan-cancer study were sourced from TCGA-pancan, encompassing 30 different cancer types and 8,650 samples. Forest plots were then generated using version 2.0.1 of the **forestplot (6)** R package. These plots were constructed based on Cox proportional hazard models, which were fitted for OS, DSS, and DFI outcomes in relation to the presence or absence of samples with EASs. The hazard ratio and 95% confidence interval were computed and utilized as the input for these plots.

Sample Phenotype and Signatures. Each EAS Signature is summarized for each sample, with the signature named after the corresponding sample ID or cell line for downstream exploration. The application includes a sample exploration tab, which allows users to examine the association between clinical features and sample groups with or without alteration signatures in each cancer type. Upon signature derivation, users have the option to further subset samples according to available molecular (e.g., FGA, TMB) and clinical (e.g., survival) features.

Drug Sensitivity and Signatures. For cell lines with EAS genes, X-AMPIE also provides a function to output the most and least sensitive drug compounds based on IC50 data clustering (7). The application also offers drug sensitivity testing between cell line groups with or without user generated amplification signatures.

Recurring EASs. This module features an onco-plot visualization (8), displaying high prevalence genes across samples for each cancer type. Users can opt to show all genes in the signatures or only those with high prevalence. The aim of the module is to identify expressed amplification genes with high frequency in specific cancer types across sample groups.

Recurring Co-occurring (RECO) EASs. RECO genes are defined as high prevalent genes that exhibit a high co-occurrence of expressed gene amplifications across samples. To extract RECO genes, high-prevalence genes are first identified, and unsupervised clustering is applied to detect their co-occurrence. The co-occurrence of genes is checked using a clustering function and visualized using onco-plots.

Gene Enrichment Analysis. Designed to explore signatures with gene set enrichment analyses, this module utilizes reference gene signatures collected by our lab and select MSigDB signatures (9) and EAS signatures generated by X-AMPIE as query signatures. Given that there may be more than 100 query EAS signatures at once, a creative visualization using onco-plot is provided to display enrichment results in a concise and informative manner, summarizing gene/pathway functions of generated EAS signatures.

Signature Crosstalk. The signature-crosstalk function, or "Crosstalk" module, is designed to discover potential relations between signatures across different cancer types using a novel adaption of gene enrichment analysis based on the hypergeometric distribution. This process requires two gene sets as input: query gene sets (application-generated signatures) and reference gene sets (either built-in, user-uploaded, or other application signatures). For each sample-level signature pair constructed, a hypergeometric distribution is applied using the two define gene sets and their significance recorded. The output demonstrates relationships across EAS signatures, representing various samples and cancer types, which are then illustrated in 2D heatmaps and oncoplots (8) at the signature levels, annotated with clinical and drug sensitivity data.

Result

The overall design of X-AMPIE for expressed amplification analyses.

The architecture of X-AMPIE revolves around the analysis of sample-level EASs. The main modules of X-AMPIE encompass three key steps: generating EAS signatures (**Figure 1A**), exploring RECO signatures (**Figure 1B**), and connecting these signatures through crosstalk analyses (**Figure 1C**). To generate EAS signatures, X-AMPIE utilizes a combination of copy number, RNA-Seq-derived- and protein-derived expression data. By integrating these data types, X-AMPIE identifies genes that exhibit both amplification and expression at the sample-level, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the functional consequences of gene amplification. The next step involves exploring RECO EASs, defined by genes that appear frequently together among sample EASs. Through a systematic analysis, X-AMPIE extracts these RECO gene combinations, revealing potential interactions and relationships among the genes that define them. Furthermore, X-AMPIE facilitates the investigation of EAS crosstalk by examining sample-level signature enrichment between sample pairs. This feature enables researchers to uncover meaningful connections and interactions not otherwise capable of analysis between different amplification signature sets, model systems and cancer types, ultimately providing insights into the broader implications of gene amplification in cancer.

The expressed amplification analyses and pan-can analyses using X-AMPIE.

We utilized X-AMPIE to analyze expressed amplification signatures (EAS) across 30 cancer types from TCGA, encompassing a total of 8,650 samples. The analysis focused on three types of EAS: amplifications, signatures with mRNA-expressed amplifications (rEAS), and signatures with protein-expressed amplifications (pEAS). The sample sizes and signature sizes for each cancer type are summarized in (**Figure 2**). Each patient sample or cell line is represented by a single EAS signature. The bar plots in Figure 2 are color-coded to indicate different types of signatures, with amplifications shown in yellow, mRNA-expressed amplifications in orange, and protein-

expressed amplifications in red. Furthermore, Figure 4B illustrates the number of samples with mRNA-expressed amplifications across the pan-cancer dataset, revealing the prevalence of mRNA-expressed amplifications across various cancer types. Additionally, Figure 4C depicts the distribution of signature sizes specifically for signatures with mRNA-expressed amplifications, providing insights into the range and variability of signature sizes across different cancer types. These pan-cancer analyses shed light on the landscape of expressed-amplification signatures and their prevalence in various cancer types, enhancing our understanding of gene amplification in cancer.

The survival analysis of samples with and without expressed amplification signatures.

We further investigated the survival outcomes associated with expressed amplification signatures across multiple cancer types (**Figure 3**). The analysis specifically examined three important endpoints: overall survival (OS), disease-specific survival (DSS), and disease-free interval survival (DFI). Figure 3A presents a forest plot illustrating the results of the overall survival analysis. The plot visually represents the hazard ratios (HR) and their corresponding confidence intervals (CI) for samples with expressed amplification compared to those without amplification. The same analysis was performed for disease-specific survival and disease-free interval survival, as depicted in Figure 3B and Figure 3C, respectively. These survival analyses contribute to our understanding of the relationship between expressed amplification signatures and clinical outcomes.

Recurring co-occurring genes with expressed amplification.

Recurring co-occurring genes are defined as highly prevalent genes that have a relatively higher co-occurrence of expressed amplification across samples (**Figure 4**). To extract RECO genes, all the genes in the EAS signatures are ranked by their prevalence across signatures. Users have the flexibility to select the top genes with high prevalence and check the co-occurrence among these genes. The app checks the co-occurrence of genes by providing a clustering function on the binary matrix converted from EAS signatures. To identify gene clusters with similar appearance patterns across samples, unsupervised clustering is performed on the rows. This process helps identify RECO genes that are highly prevalent across samples and co-occur in a significant number of samples. Further clustering of the columns (samples) enables identification of sample clusters that can be associated with gene clusters for downstream analysis.

As a case study, we examined the prevalence of expressed amplification signatures (EAS) and oncogenes in pancreatic and colorectal cancer. Figure 4A presents the prevalence of the top 20 EAS genes across the entire genome in colorectal cancer progressor samples (n=199), visualized using an onco-plot and sorted by their prevalence. For comparison, we also analyzed the prevalence of the top 20 EAS genes within the oncogenes group, which exhibited a lower prevalence of EAS genes. The co-occurring group of top recurring genes (RECO) is depicted in Figure 4C.

Additionally, we provided a summary of the prevalence of common samples, including the gene groups of top recurring genes, top oncogenes, and the RECO1-6 gene groups. These analyses were also performed for pancreatic cancer, with a sample size of 128 progressor samples.

Overall, the RECO gene extraction method provides a powerful tool for identifying highly prevalent genes with significant co-occurrence of expressed amplification across samples. With clustering function integrated, it further provides insight of the connection of the RECO genes and associated sample clusters.

Crosstalk of expressed amplification signatures

From previous module, X-AMPIE extracts expressed amplification signatures for each cancer type. To further investigate these signatures and explore common/distinct genes across cancer types, a signature-crosstalk function (The "Crosstalk" module for signature exploration) has been developed to examine potential connections between signatures (Figure 1C).

The method behind crosstalk is a novel adaptation of gene enrichment analysis based on hypergeometric distribution. The inputs of the crosstalk modules include two groups of gene sets the query gene sets, and the reference gene sets. The query signatures are generated by the app, whereas reference signatures can not only come from the app but also be in various formats such as built-in gene sets like amplicons and hallmark, or other user-defined signatures such as PDO/PDX signatures. For background genes, for gene sets from specific cancer types, the amplified genes from the cancer types are used. The output results are the relationship across signatures and visualized in oncoplots with clinical and drug sensitivity information as annotations if available.

For crosstalk, the query and reference gene sets (signatures) can be customized based on biological questions and analyzed using various combinational patterns. To elaborate the query signatures and reference signatures, EAS genes are taken as an example to explain this concept further. To illustrate this, the "Crosstalk" module can be utilized to explore EAS signatures from several perspective: 1) First, the Crosstalk module can be applied to examine the relationship between a set of EAS signatures from a single source for a particular cancer type. In this case, the query genes can be any public or in-house populated signatures, like hallmark genes from MSigDB (9) or targetable genes from OncoKB (10). Alternatively, users can upload their own gene lists as reference gene sets. 2) The second example involves investigating the signature relationship between EAS signatures from different sources within a single cancer type extracted from patient samples and cell lines. 3) The third scenario aims to analyze the relationships between expression amplification signatures from diverse cancer types generated by a single data source. Additionally,

the Crosstalk module can be used to explore the connection between EAS generated from different expression data types. For example, users can investigate the mRNA-high EAS and protein-high EAS in breast cancer cell lines.

To provide an example of crosstalk analysis, we present the case of pancreatic and colorectal cancer (Figure 5). These two cancer types share common genomic features, including germline mutations in BRCA1 and BRCA2 (11), presence of KRAS mutations (12), and genetic alterations governing cancer progression, such as gene expression changes, copy number aberrations, chromosomal rearrangements, and epigenetic alterations (13). For the crosstalk analysis, colorectal cancer signatures ($n = 173$) are used as the reference gene sets, while pancreatic cancer signatures ($n = 102$) act as the query. The heatmap visualization demonstrates the number of overlapping genes between the two sets, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Further analysis involves visualizing the reference signatures (top 25%) from colorectal cancer ($n = 40$) that exhibit the highest number of overlaps with all the query EAS signatures from pancreatic cancer ($n = 102$). Notably, the early progression group within the query pancreatic cancer samples shows the highest number of overlapping genes compared to the medium and late progression groups. This crosstalk analysis reveals that early progressors in both colorectal and pancreatic cancer share a significant number of expressed amplification genes ($n=4,040$) compared to other gene groups. These findings shed light on potential commonalities and interactions between early progressors in these two cancer types.

In summary, the Crosstalk module within X-AMPIE provides researchers with a powerful tool to explore the complex relationships between different gene signatures. By uncovering the connections and interactions between expressed amplification signatures, researchers can gain valuable insights into the underlying biology of various diseases.

Discussion

Gene amplification is a critical molecular mechanism in cancer development and progression, contributing to the dysregulation of key genes involved in cell growth, survival, and signaling pathways. Understanding the landscape of expressed amplification signatures and their implications in cancer biology is crucial for identifying potential therapeutic targets and improving patient outcomes. X-AMPIE serves a comprehensive and user-friendly tool that enables the generation, exploration, and connection of expressed amplification signatures in cancer.

One of the key advantages of X-AMPIE is its ability to integrate gene expression and copy number alteration data, to identify genes that are both overexpressed and amplified in cancer cells. By combining these data, X-AMPIE provides a more comprehensive understanding of the functional

consequences of gene amplification and gene expression, allowing researchers to delve deeper into the underlying molecular mechanisms of cancer.

The "crosstalk" function in X-AMPIE is a particularly valuable feature that enables the investigation of potential connections and interactions between different amplification signature sets. By examining the crosstalk between different cancer types and model systems, researchers can uncover novel insights into the relationships between amplification signatures and potentially identify common biological mechanisms underlying cancer progression.

Through the pan-cancer analysis conducted using X-AMPIE, we observed the prevalence of expressed amplifications across various cancer types. This highlights the importance of considering the integration of data modalities when studying gene amplification in cancer. By incorporating expression data, X-AMPIE provides a more comprehensive view of the functional consequences of gene amplification and allows for a more accurate characterization of the landscape of expressed amplification signatures.

The extraction of recurring co-occurring genes (RECO) from the expressed amplification signatures further enhances our understanding of the relationships between genes in the context of gene amplification. By identifying highly prevalent genes that co-occur frequently within the signatures, X-AMPIE uncovers potential interactions and functional relationships between these genes. This information can provide valuable insights into the underlying biology of cancer and guide the identification of potential biomarkers and therapeutic targets.

Future enhancements to X-AMPIE could include the integration of additional data types, such as DNA methylation and histone modification data, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the epigenetic landscape of gene amplification in cancer.

In conclusion, X-AMPIE is a powerful tool that empowers researchers to explore, analyze, and connect expressed amplification signatures in cancer. By leveraging omics data and incorporating the "crosstalk" function, X-AMPIE facilitates a deeper understanding of the landscape of gene amplification in cancer biology. It offers valuable insights into potential therapeutic targets, clinical implications, and shared features across different cancer types. X-AMPIE has the potential to accelerate research in the field of gene amplification and contribute to the development of more effective personalized treatment strategies for cancer patients.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge Wenxuan Jiang for help with the forest plots and hazard ratio analyses. The website of X-AMPIE is hosted on an AWS server provided by the Kowalski Lab and is supported by UT-Austin IT solutions and Dell Medical School at UT-Austin.

Author contributions: Q.X. designed the platform, implemented the workflows, performed the analyses, drafted the figures and initial manuscript. J.K. conceived of the idea, directed the analyses, and edited the manuscript.

Funding

This work was supported by the University of Texas Dell Medical School Research Funds [to JK].

Conflict of Interest: none declared.

References

1. Albertson DG. Gene amplification in cancer. *Trends in Genetics*. 2006;22(8):447-55. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2006.06.007>.
2. Tanaka H, Watanabe T. Mechanisms Underlying Recurrent Genomic Amplification in Human Cancers. *Trends Cancer*. 2020;6(6):462-77. Epub 2020/05/10. doi: 10.1016/j.trecan.2020.02.019. PubMed PMID: 32383436; PMCID: PMC7285850.
3. Tomczak K, Czerwińska P, Wiznerowicz M. The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA): an immeasurable source of knowledge. *Contemporary oncology*. 2015;19(1A):A68.
4. Cerami E, Gao J, Dogrusoz U, Gross BE, Sumer SO, Aksoy BA, Jacobsen A, Byrne CJ, Heuer ML, Larsson E, Antipin Y, Reva B, Goldberg AP, Sander C, Schultz N. The cBio cancer genomics portal: an open platform for exploring multidimensional cancer genomics data. *Cancer Discov*. 2012;2(5):401-4. doi: 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-12-0095. PubMed PMID: 22588877; PMCID: PMC3956037.
5. Goldman MJ, Craft B, Hastie M, Repečka K, McDade F, Kamath A, Banerjee A, Luo Y, Rogers D, Brooks AN, Zhu J, Haussler D. Visualizing and interpreting cancer genomics data via the Xena platform. *Nature Biotechnology*. 2020;38(6):675-8. doi: 10.1038/s41587-020-0546-8.
6. Gordon M, Lumley T, Gordon MM. Package 'forestplot'. Advanced forest plot using 'grid'graphics The Comprehensive R Archive Network, Vienna. 2019.
7. Yang W, Soares J, Greninger P, Edelman EJ, Lightfoot H, Forbes S, Bindal N, Beare D, Smith JA, Thompson IR, Ramaswamy S, Futreal PA, Haber DA, Stratton MR, Benes C, McDermott U, Garnett MJ. Genomics of Drug Sensitivity in Cancer (GDSC): a resource for therapeutic biomarker discovery in cancer cells. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2013;41(Database issue):D955-61. Epub 2012/11/28. doi: 10.1093/nar/gks1111. PubMed PMID: 23180760; PMCID: PMC3531057.
8. Gu Z, Eils R, Schlesner M. Complex heatmaps reveal patterns and correlations in multidimensional genomic data. *Bioinformatics*. 2016;32(18):2847-9. Epub 2016/05/22. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btw313. PubMed PMID: 27207943.
9. Liberzon A, Birger C, Thorvaldsdóttir H, Ghandi M, Mesirov JP, Tamayo P. The Molecular Signatures Database (MSigDB) hallmark gene set collection. *Cell Syst*. 2015;1(6):417-25. Epub 2016/01/16. doi: 10.1016/j.cels.2015.12.004. PubMed PMID: 26771021; PMCID: PMC4707969.
10. Chakravarty D, Gao J, Phillips SM, Kundra R, Zhang H, Wang J, Rudolph JE, Yaeger R, Soumerai T, Nissan MH, Chang MT, Chandarlapaty S, Traina TA, Paik PK, Ho AL, Hantash FM, Grupe A, Baxi SS, Callahan MK, Snyder A, Chi P, Danila D, Gounder M, Harding JJ, Hellmann MD, Iyer G, Janjigian Y, Kaley T, Levine DA, Lowery M, Omuro A, Postow MA, Rathkopf D, Shoushtari AN, Shukla N, Voss M, Paraiso E, Zehir A, Berger MF, Taylor BS, Saltz LB, Riely GJ, Ladanyi M, Hyman DM, Baselga J, Sabbatini P, Solit DB, Schultz N. OncoKB: A Precision Oncology Knowledge Base. *JCO Precis Oncol*. 2017;2017. Epub 20170516. doi: 10.1200/PO.17.00011. PubMed PMID: 28890946; PMCID: PMC5586540.
11. Underhill ML, Germansky KA, Yurgelun MB. Advances in Hereditary Colorectal and Pancreatic Cancers. *Clinical Therapeutics*. 2016;38(7):1600-21. doi: 10.1016/j.clinthera.2016.03.017.
12. Zhu G, Pei L, Xia H, Tang Q, Bi F. Role of oncogenic KRAS in the prognosis, diagnosis and treatment of colorectal cancer. *Molecular Cancer*. 2021;20(1). doi: 10.1186/s12943-021-01441-4.

13. Wang S, Zheng Y, Yang F, Zhu L, Zhu X-Q, Wang Z-F, Wu X-L, Zhou C-H, Yan J-Y, Hu B-Y, Kong B, Fu D-L, Bruns C, Zhao Y, Qin L-X, Dong Q-Z. The molecular biology of pancreatic adenocarcinoma: translational challenges and clinical perspectives. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*. 2021;6(1). doi: 10.1038/s41392-021-00659-4.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Overview of signature analysis features of X-AMPIE. (A) Generating signature: X-AMPIE generates expressed amplification signatures using copy number, RNA expression, and protein expression data. (B) The introduction of recurring co-occurring (RECO) genes and the extraction of them from expressed amplification signatures. (C) The instances of different signature combinations as inputs for the crosstalk module to address various biological questions in the context of cancer. Illustration of the crosstalk module and its outputs of expressed amplification genes, visualized in the onco-plot format.

Figure 2. Pan-can analyses of samples and genes of expressed-amplification signatures. (A) The number of expressed-amplified signatures (EASs) and sample sizes for each cancer type using data from pan-cancer TCGA and CCLE projects, summarizing one signature for each patient sample or cell line. The bar plots are color the different types of signatures in terms of signatures with amplifications (AS, yellow), signatures with mRNA-expressed amplifications (rEAS, orange) and protein-expressed amplifications (pEAS, red). (B) The number of samples with mRNA-expressed amplifications (orange) signature in pan-can. (C) The distribution of signature sizes for each cancer type for signatures with mRNA-expressed amplifications.

Figure 3. Survival analysis of samples with expressed amplification and not across pan-can. (A) The forest plot for overall survival (OS) (B) The forest plot for disease specific survival (DSS). (C) The forest plot for disease free interval survival (DFI).

Figure.4 The prevalence comparison of expressed amplification signatures (EAS) and oncogenes in pancreatic and colorectal cancer. (A) The prevalence of top 20 EAS genes genome wide in colorectal cancer (n = 199 progressor samples), visualized in the onco-plot sorted by their prevalence. (B) The co-occurring group of top recurring genes (RECO). (C) The prevalence summary of common samples of gene group including Top-RECO genes, RECO1-6 gene groups. (D-F) The results of EAS prevalence analyses in pancreatic cancer (n = 128 progressor samples).

Figure.5 The crosstalk analysis between cancer types using colorectal and pancreatic cancer progressors. (A) The crosstalk between expressed amplification signatures from pancreatic and colorectal progressors. The colorectal signatures (n = 173) are used as the reference gene sets and the pancreatic signatures (n = 102) as the query. The number of genes overlapped are visualized in the heatmap (p < 0.05). The signatures/sample are further grouped by their progression groups (EP: early progression, MP: medium progression, LP: late progression). (B) A 2D heatmap visualization of the top 25% reference signatures (colorectal, n = 40) that have the highest number of overlapped with all the query EAS signature (pancreatic, n = 102).

Figure 1

A Expressed Amplification Signature Generation

B Gene-level: Recurring Co-occurring (RECO)

C Crosstalk of EAS

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

A

Pancreatic Cancer

B

